

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

Flight Data Catalogue

Flight A445

28 March 1996

Satellite Calibration Validation

For more information contact:

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A445 Profile3

| Non Deiced True Temp

| Dew Point (GE)

| Dew Point (TW)

A445 Profile2

| Non Deiced True Temp

| Dew Point (GE)

| Dew Point (TW)

A445 Profile1

| Non Deiced True Temp

| Dew Point (GE)

| Dew Point (TW)

A445 Profile3

Non Deiced True Temp

Dew Point (GE)

Dew Point (TW)

A445 Profile2

| Non Deiced True Temp

| Dew Point (GE)

| Dew Point (TW)

A445 Profile1

Non Deiced True Temp

Dew Point (GE)

Dew Point (TW)

A445 Profile3

| Non Deiced True Temp

| Dew Point (GE)

| Dew Point (TW)

A445 Profile2

| Non Deiced True Temp

| Dew Point (GE)

| Dew Point (TW)

A445 Profile1

Non Deiced True Temp

Dew Point (GE)

Dew Point (TW)

A445 Profile3

| Non Deiced True Temp | Dew Point (GE) Dew Point (TW)

A445 Profile2

| Non Deiced True Temp | Dew Point (GE) | Dew Point (TW)

A445 Profile

| Non Deiced True Temp | Dew Point (GE) | Dew Point (TW)

AVHRR

28 MARCH 1996

13:19

AVHRZ

28 MARCH 1996

13:19

AVHRR

28 MARCH 1996

13:19

AVHRR
28 MARCH 1996
13:19

AVHRR
28 MARCH 1996
11:39 am

AVHRR

28 MARCH 1996

11:39 am

AVHRR

28 MARCH 1996

11:39 am

AVHRR
27 MARCH 1996
13:29

AVHRR

27 MARCH 1996

13:29

AVHRR

27 MARCH 1996

11:50 AM

AVHRR
27 MARCH 1996
11:50 AM

AVHRR

27 MARCH 1996

13:29

AVHRR

28 MARCH 1996

13:19

AVHRR

28 MARCH 1996

11:39 AM

Meteosat-IR 280596 1300GMT

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. A 445

DATE: 28 103 / 95

Take off : 10 : 45

Landing : 14 : 35

Aircraft Scientist	: A. KAYE	Captain	: SQN LDR C. O'BRIAN
Flight Leader	: D PERCIVAL	Co-pilot	: FLT LT M PURSE
Others	: J HENT	Navigator	: FLT LT J CANNING
	H GREENSMITH	Engineer	: MA. ENG K QUICK
	M PICHERING	Loadmaster	: FLT SGT J LAW
	S WILSON		
SF(26)	L HAY		
	C DONLAN		

Trial Instructions :
Operating area : BRISTOL CHANNEL

General synoptic situation

TIME : 12Z

FLIGHT REPORT A445 28/03/96 ATSR II CAL_VAL

Time 1	E.M.	Time 2	E.M.	Event	Height	Heading	OMEGA LAT/LONG for start and end of Run.
08:14:39				Data On.			Start Up at 51°09.85N 001°44.61W
10:46:00				TAKE OFF			BOSCOMBE DOWN
11:03:58 (20)		11:14:35 (21)		Climb to transit height			
				Transit	FL260	290°	Transit to Bristol Channel
11:14:35 (21)		11:34:25 (22)		Profile 1	FL260 FL060	300°	1000'/min
11:34:25 (22)		11:46:11 (24)		P 1 cont	FL060 50 ft	290°	500'/min
							N51°04.6' W004°12.2' to N51°34.4' W006°36.1'
11:47:59 (25)		12:08:15 (26)		Run 1	100 ft	115°	
							N51°32.9' W006°35.1' to N51°15.3' W004°53.3'
12:09:35 (27)		12:31:47 (28)		Run 2	100 ft	290°	
							N51°16.5' W004°53.6' to N51°30.6' W006°28.0'
12:32:14 (29)		12:39:42 (30)		Profile 2	50 ft FL040	300°	500'/min
12:39:42 (30)		12:57:37 (31)		P 2 cont	FL040 FL210	110°/300°	1000'/min
							N51°30.9' W006°29.9' to N51°29.2' W006°20.3'
13:01:16 (32)		13:16:49 (33)		Run 3	FL175	110°	Aerosol layer.
							N51°27.5' W006°31.8' to N51°13.2' W004°45.0'
13:23:21 (34)		13:44:55 (35)		Run 4	100 ft	290°	
							Run cut short due to bird strike. Return to base.
							N51°13.1' W004°50.3' to N51°30.1' W006°18.8'
13:47:06 (36)		13:56:05 (38)		Profile 3	200' FL030	100°	500'/min
13:56:05 (38)		14:00:33 (39)		P 3 cont	FL030 FL100	090°	1000'/min
							N51°32.7' W006°18.8' to N51°22.5' W005°05.4'
14:00:33 (39)		14:10:32 (40)		Run 5	FL100	110°	AERIES RUN
							N51°22.5' W005°05.4' to N51°18.3' W004°04.9'
14:35:42				LAND AT			Boscombe Down
14:41:39				Data off.			Shut down at 51°09.68N 001°44.31W

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne
Support Facility

Sea Surface Temperature and Aerosol Experiment

Date: 23/3/96

Flight No: A445

- SORTIE OBJECTIVE:** To provide a sea surface temperature and aerosol number density and mode size data for model validation and calibration for ATSR I/II.
- LOCATION:** South West approaches as dictated by location of satellite track as shown on attached map.
- WEATHER:** Clear sky conditions, no cirrus cloud although some cumulus clouds can be tolerated.
- FLIGHT PATTERN:** [1] Transit to operating area at suitable altitude.
- Follow flight pattern as show in attached diagram. The runs should be timed such that the satellite passes over at about the mid-point of the 100 ft run.*
- [2] High level run >F1200, 50-100 miles. (20 min)
 - [3] Execute a profile from current level to 50 ft in cloud free air if possible. Profile at @1,000 ft/min down to top of boundary layer and then @500 ft/min to minimum safe altitude. (30 min)
 - [4] 100 ft run along line of satellite track, >100 miles. Overpass occurs halfway along run. (35 minutes)
 - [5] Reciprocal run at _____ft at level of maximum aerosol concentration. (35 min)
 - [6] Profile from 50 ft (or minimum safe altitude) at 500 ft/min to top of boundary layer and the @1,000 ft/min to flight level of original high level run (30 min)
 - [7] High level run >F1200, 50-100 miles. (20 min)
 - [8] Transit back to base.
- TOTAL DURATION:** 3 Hours on task

Natural
Environment
Research
Council

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne
Support Facility

Sea Surface Temperature and Aerosol Experiment

Date: 28/3/96

Flight No: A445

Flight planning diagram

ATSR 1 - Wednesday 27 March
ATSR 2 - Thursday 28 March.

Western Approaches, ATSR-1 crossing
50.0 N 27th March 1996 at 11:27:15 UTC
ESA/ESTEC/NW, ERS-1, 35-day repeat orbit (501), 58.337 deg First Orbit 24574 Last Orbit 24574

ATSR FRIDAY 28 March

Western Approaches, ATSR-1 crossing
50.0 N 28th March 1996 at 22:17:50 UTC
ESA/ESTEC/NW, ERS-1, 35-day repeat orbit (501), 58.337 deg First Orbit 24595 Last Orbit 24595

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *A. Kung'u*

Project: . Date: *28/3/16*
 Flight No: *A445* Page *4* of *4*

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
<i>13:59:08</i>		<i>P3</i>	<i>10.4</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>89</i>	<i>51.37</i>	<i>-5.12</i>	<i>peak in ozone.</i>	
<i>14:00:36</i>		<i>P5</i> <i>R5</i>	<i>100</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>85</i>	<i>51.37</i>	<i>-5.05</i>	<i>1/8 cu below haze layer visible clear above.</i>	
<i>14:04:40</i>	<i>39</i>	<i>R5</i>	<i>110</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>82</i>	<i>51.34</i>	<i>-4.65</i>	<i>2/8 cu approaching Sc. clear above.</i>	
<i>14:09:50</i>	<i>"</i>	<i>R5</i>	<i>110</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>81</i>	<i>51.31</i>	<i>-4.13</i>	<i>7/8 Sc Below; clear above.</i>	
<i>14:10:32</i>	<i>"</i>	<i>R52</i>	<i>110</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>88</i>	<i>51.31</i>	<i>-4.07</i>	<i>7/8 Same</i>	
<hr/>									
<i>END OF SCIENCE</i>									
<hr/>									

Aircraft Scientist: A. Knight

Flight No: A 445 Page 3 of 4

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
						12:49:31			
								(17200) first peak.	
12:57:56		P2e	FL130 FL110		295	51.50	-6.40	Dropping back to FL172.	
13:01:16		R3	F174		101	51.45	-6.46	Picked out Max aerosol layer for Aerosol run.	
13:16:27		R3	F174		87	51.22	-4.77		
13:16:49		R3	F174		87	"	"	< 1/8 cu cu below clear above.	
13:20								spiral Decent.	
13:23:20		R4	100	R	282	51.22	-4.86	1/8 cu cu & hazy. 1021 4/5	
13:33:50		R4	100	R	264	51.37	-5.57	negligible wiffs of cu hazy & no cloud.	
13:45:*								Bird strike. end of Run.	
13:47:07		P3	200	R	98	51.54	-6.24	Profile from 200 ft.	
13:53:58		P3	36	P	100	51.47	-5.61	< 1/8 cu below Solid Sc on horizon clear above.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Venz

Project: SOC Date: 28/3/96
Flight No: A445 Page 2 of 4

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
11:55:05	25	R1	100	R					
11:58:06	✓	R1	100	R	107	51.40 -5.72	Clear + a few contrails.		
12:06:00	✓	R1	100	R	100	51.28 -5.06	clear cloudy Island visible ahead in haze.		
12:08:15		R1e	100	R	99	51.25 -4.87	Sc sheet ahead end run and turn about.		
12:09:37		R2	100	R	285	51.27 -4.91	25-30 min.	12:40 30 13:10	
12:14:37		R2	100	R	285	51.32 -5.29	Clear!		
12:24:33	27	R2	100	R	283	51.43 -5.96	& just passed under a region of very small Broken cu.		
12:27:48		R2e	100	R	284	51.51 -6.49	.		
12:32:14		P2	50	R	283	51.52 -6.54	1021 Sea state 4-5 hazy, clear		
12:36:12		P2					Wing left hand turn. in climb.		
12:39:33		P2	4.0k		98	51.45 -6.76	1000/min		
12:42:02		P2	6.9		96	51.43 -6.88	hazy below some cloud visible on horizon clear above.		

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye

Project: ~~Game~~ Date: 23/3/76

Flight No: A445 Page # of 4

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
10:51:46	19	T	11700	P	270	51.09	-2.27	clear above No cirrus 6/8 cu and hazy below.	
10:56:42	19	T	14.3		281	51.06	-2.58	clear above 6/8 cu below but clear towards Bristol channel.	
10:59:45		T	22.5		284	51.05	-2.78	5/8 cu below solid to south. clear ahead.	
11:04:19	20	T	25.9		291	51.06	-3.11	4/8 cu below clear ahead.	
11:08:17		T	26.0		281	51.09	-3.49	5/8 cu over land large clear patch ahead.	
11:14:39	21	P1	26.0		297	51.09	-4.26	very hazy due to aerosol layer clear otherwise.	
11:24:05			16000 ft					video dump of Aerosol 5/16 feet below peak	
11:32:01		P1	8.4		305	51.49	-5.56	hazy & no no cloud some patches of oil visible from Millard Haven.	
11:34:24		P1	6.0		282	51.53	-5.69	No cloud hazy slight adjustment to keep in clearest space.	
11:40:23		P1	2.4		280	51.55	-6.17	(210 685) Aerosol. very hazy but no cloud.	
11:45:14		P1e	50	R	274	51.57	-6.56	hazy & clear 102' sea state 4/5	
11:47:59		R1	100	R	106	51.55	-6.62	Clear! SUNNY!	

AS AL44

POST FLIGHT REQUIREMENTS FORM

Flight No: A445 Date: 28 MAR 96 A/S Name: HAYE

Aircraft Scientist's Post Flight Requirements:

1. Are any copies of the flight folder required?
YES NO for 2 FOR MADLEY AN. SOUTHAMPTON

2. Flight data and folders will normally be discarded after 10 years, is this OK?
YES NO If not OK, state period

3. Is the flight part of an international project or major campaign?
YES NO Name of Project

4. Do you want the video tape kept?
YES NO How long? 10 YRS 1 COPY

5. Has the Handheld camera or the Camcorder been used:
YES NO VIDEO
If yes, do you want the handheld camera film processed:
immediately or when the film is finished?

6. Do you want the cloud physics data kept?
YES NO
If yes, which disc / file do you want it stored in? ... MRF 14: [.....]

7. Do you want to do the interactive processing?
YES NO

NOTE:

- Members of MRF Radiation and Cloud Physics groups are expected to meet their own requirements for data storage and non-standard processing.
- For non MRF users, Data Management Section will keep the processed data TEMPORARILY until the requirements are made known.
- Any other requirements for post-flight processing and data storage should be discussed with the Data Management Section.
- If copies of the Flight Folder are required, it is the responsibility of the Aircraft Scientist / User to produce them.

Interactive Processing Log

Flight No. A445 Date: 2203 96 User: KAYE INERC
Interactive by: D PERCIUAL A KAYE
Date: 0204 96

Renav

Vel N	OK	Pos N	OK
Vel E	OK	Pos E	OK

TWC

Profile plotted : P2
Line chosen : Profile / ~~Whole flight~~ / ~~Other~~

a = - -0.1237 E +1
b = + 0.7118 E -04
c = + 0.1807 E -05

OK

LWC

~~OK~~ LARGE OFFSET - INSTRUMENT PROBLEMS?

Heimann / Barnes

OK

LIQUID WATER CONTENT

A446

MENU

LIQUID_WATER

FSSP

2DC

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: A445 Date: 28 03 96

Page!.....of 3

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES		
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT	
0908	REF +	5	0564	✓		Approx 0568		
	REF -	7	3075	✓		Approx 3071		
	AOSS	19	1704	2.0	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	6000	3.5	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	0000	✓		As Indicated 0000		
	PR HT	8	3268	0.4	315	As Altimeter		
	CABP	14	3973	1000				
	A/S	9	0076	✓		As ASI 0000 - 0100		
	UP1S	81	1354	430	431			
	UP2S	82	1253	222	244			
	UIRS	83	1244	-41	310			
	UP1Z	84	0151	✓		Approx 0147		
0915	UP2Z	85	0145	✓		Approx 0149		
	UIRZ	86	2033	✓		Approx 2061		
	UP1T	87	2721	5		As IAT		
	UP2T	88	2734	5	4.1	As IAT		
	UIRT	89	2744	5		As IAT		
	LP1S	91	0268	44	46			
	LP2S	92	0178	5	4			
	LIRS	93	1987	-14	349			
	LP1Z	94	0151	✓		Approx 0150		
	LP2Z	95	0161	✓		Approx 0146		
	LIRZ	96	2049	✓		Approx 2050		
	LP1T	97	2701	7	4.5	As IAT		
	LP2T	98	2575	13		As IAT		
	LIRT	99	2714	6.5		As IAT		
	J/W	42	996			As Indicated 0000		
	NEPH	47	XXXX					
	HYGR	58	2414	-2.5	-2.1			
	HYCC	59	0710	✓		696-901		
	FDEW	138	4095			DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C		
	FSTA	139	4095					
	DTF	10	2063	7	6.1			
	DTC	11	5					
	NDTF	23	1227	4	4.0	same as De-Iced		
	NDTC	24	5					
	INCT	48	4095					
	CCN	140	4095			less than 4095 if ON		
	TWCD	70	1422	✓		0000-4094		
	TSAM	72	1431	✓		0640-1860 < min		
	O3	100	0001					
	O3P	106	1320	673		$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145m.B$		
	O3RG	113	1979					
0930								

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
0936	FL NO	1	Hex	445	/		Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0093			Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0704	093704	/	Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	11-12	/		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
				40	95		
	LATC	160	Dec	0000			Latitude
	LONGC	161	Dec	0000			Longitude
937							

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: *PRE FLIGHT*

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
0938	TWCD	70	1440	/		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	826	/		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	0060	/		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2157	/		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2234	/		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	2072	/		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2136	/		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1025	/		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4089	/		4095	
	EV1V	170	2043				
	EV2V	171	2043				
	NPWR	172	3526				
	EVIC	173	3968				
0944	EV2C	174	3968				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOMES	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	☒ Off / On	Large / ☒ Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	☒ Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's ~~Pre~~/In-Flight Check List

CHEK Flight No: A445 Date: 220346
for auto selection

Page.....of 3

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1055	REF +	5	562	/		Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	3071	/		Approx 3071	
	AOSS	19	2256	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	0826	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	4095	FL200		As Indicated 0000	
	PR HT	8	1752	260	FL260	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	3371	340	/		
	A/S	9	960	155	156	As ASI 0000 - 0100	
	UP1S	81	2312	780	779		
	UP2S	82	2029	388	432		
	UIRS	83	1755	-60	138		
	UP1Z	84	163	/		Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	166	/		Approx 0149	
	UIRZ	86	2094	/		Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	3458	-30	-40	As IAT	
	UP2T	88	3495	-30		As IAT	
	UIRT	89	3597	-34	-39	As IAT	
1106	LP1S	91	0527	147	148		
	LP2S	92	500	90	81		
	LIRS	93	2435	75	258		
	LP1Z	94	0153	/		Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95	173	/		Approx 0146	
	LIRZ	96	2062	/		Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97	3625	-35	-33.8	As IAT	
	LP2T	98	3563	-32		As IAT	
	LIRT	99	3611	-34		As IAT	
	J/W	42	2830			As Indicated 0000	
	NEPH	47	X				
	HYGR	58	1055	-46	-45		
	HYCC	59	0814	/		696-901	
	FDEW	138	4095	3		DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	4095				
	DTF	10	255	-31			
	DTC	11	2583		-31		
	NDTF	23	252	-31		same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	3				
	INCT	48	4095				
	CCN	140	4095			less than 4095 if ON	
	TWCD	70	917	/		0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	1122	/		0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100	166				
	O3P	106	1914	911.6		$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$	
	O3RG	113	1802				
1112							

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
1129	FL NO	1	Hex	445	/		Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0112	/		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	943	112943	/	Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	0021	/		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
				W	0	9	5
	LATC	160	Dec	0585	51'28.48N		Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	4034	-5°0'22.8W		Longitude
1131							

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height:

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1138	TWCD	70	1286	/		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	2508	/		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	1255	/		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2602	/		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2235	/		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	2252	/		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	3140	/		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1024	/		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4095			4095	
	EV1V	170	3474				
	EV2V	171	3138				
	NPWR	172	2700				
	EVIC	173	4019				
1143	EV2C	174	4021				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: A445 Date: 280396

Page.....of 3

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1212	REF +	5	0568	/		Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	3072	/		Approx 3071	
	AOSS	19	2143	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	1220	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	0082			As Indicated 0000	
1220	PR HT	8	3921	1015	1016	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	4095				
	A/S	9	1400	127	125	As ASI 0000 - 0100	
	UP1S	81	1965	650	630		
	UP2S	82	1678	300	323		
	UIRS	83	1842	-40	322		
1225	UP1Z	84	152	/		Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	147	/		Approx 0149	
	UIRZ	86	2040	/		Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	2648	10	10.3	As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2666	9		As IAT	
	UIRT	89	2688	8		As IAT	
	LP1S	91	0230	27	33		
	LP2S	92	178	10	9		
	LIRS	93	1981	-15	350		
	LP1Z	94	150	/		Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95	161	/		Approx 0146	
1236	LIRZ	96	2064	/		Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97	2723	5	5.6	As IAT	
	LP2T	98	2706	7		As IAT	
	LIRT	99	2734	5		As IAT	
	J/W	42	3143	1.3		As Indicated 0000	
	NEPH	47	2347				
	HYGR	58	2347	-5.8	-5.2		
	HYCC	59	0738	/		696-901	
	FDEW	138	4095			DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	4095				
	DTF	10	1233	4			
	DTC	11	5		3.8		
	NDTF	23	969	4		same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	5				
	INCT	48	4095				
	CCN	140	4095			less than 4095 if ON	
	TWCD	70	1042	/		0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	1344	/		0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100	178				
	O3P	106	3152	1405.8		$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$	
	O3RG	113	1772				
1244							

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
1325	FL NO	1	Hex	0145	445	1445	Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0132		/	Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0609	132619	/	Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	0034	/		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
				4	0	9	5
	LATC	160	Dec	0583	51° 18' 24"		Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	4038	-4° 39' 21.6"		Longitude
1327							

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: 100ft

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1328	TWCD	70	1486	/		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	2521	/		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	1367	/		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2691	/		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2248	/		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	1363	/		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2399	/		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1025	/		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4045	/		4095	
	EV1V	170	3474	/			
	EV2V	171	3140	/			
	NPWR	172	2698	/			
	EVIC	173	4022	/			
1339	EV2C	174	4001	/			

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

FLIGHT LEADER'S IN-FLIGHT LOG

Date 280396 Flight No. A445

Page 1 of 1

VIDEO TAPE

No. A445#1
Ends 140810

- DFC
- RFC
- FFC

	GPS	INU <i>Realign ok</i>
Lat.	51° N 09 85	51° N 09 85
Long.	001 44-61 W	001 44-60 W
Time	0904	0905

DRS recording to HORACE

HORACE recording to optical disk

SATCOM sending position reports

Time GMT	Event No	HT	QNH	HDG	IAS	TAS	TAT	D.P.	D.I. Htr.		
091439						DATA ON					
101758	19					Start up.					
104600						Take off					
						Boscombe Down					
						Climb to Transit level.					
						Level TRANSIT					
110359	20	FL260	1013	290	150	111	-45	-46	OFF		
						START PROFILE					
111435	21	FL260	1013	300	180	131	-42	-45	OFF	1000/min.	
						Reduce to 500 ^{ft} /min.					
113425	22	FL260	1013	390	180	95.2	-3.1	-2.9	OFF	520/min.	
						END PI					
114611	24	50 ^{ft}	1021	285	180	87.6	5.0	-2	OFF	SS = 415	
						START R1					
114759	25	100 ^{ft}	1021	110	180	90.6	4.8	-1.7	OFF		
						END R1					
120815	26	100 ^{ft}	1021	115	180	90.1	4.5	-1.1	OFF		
						START R2					
20935	27	100 ^{ft}	1021	290	180	88.8	4.6	-1.2	OFF		

Video Tape ok? 1410.

TIME GMT	EVENT NO	HT	QNH	HDG	IAS	TAS	TAT	D.P.	D.I. Htr.		
					END	RUN 2					
123147	28	100 ^{ft}	1021	240	180	88	4.6	-1.2	OFF		
					START	P 2	↗				
123214	29	50 ^{ft}	1021	240	180	87	4.9	-1.2	OFF	SS = 45 ^{sec/m}	
					Readjust to	100 ^{ft}					
123942	30	FLOW	1013	110	180	94	-3.7	-6.4	OFF		
					END	P 2.					
125737	31	FL210	1013	300	180	125	-30	-36	OFF		
					START	RUN 3					
130116	32	FL174	1013	110	180	116	-2.2	-2.8	OFF		
					END	R 3					
131649	33	FL175	1013	110	180	117	-21.5	-27.5	OFF		
					Descent to	100 ^{ft}					
					START	RUN 4					
132321	34	100 ^{ft}	1021	290	140	95	5.1	0.2	OFF	SS = 415	
					END	RUN 4				BIRD STRIKE	
134455	35	100 ^{ft}	1021	240	180	94	4.1	-0.3	OFF		
					START	P 3	↗				
134706	36	200 ^{ft}	1021	100	180	91	4.3	-0.4	OFF	500	
135605	37	FL030	1013							1000 ^{ft} /m	
140033	38	FL			END	P 3 / R 5					
		FL100	1013	090	185	110	-2.0	-36.1	OFF		
					END	R 5					
141038	40	FL100	1013	110	180	109	-2.5	-41.6	OFF		
143542	...			LAND	AAE						

14 4139.

DATA OFF 5100' EPM 3:50

OZONE ANALYZER LOG

Project: NERC

Date: 2/21/96

User: JSS

Flight No: A445

Page 1 of 3

GMT	RUN #	HEIGHT	OZONE	SCALE	REMARKS (e.g. changes in pressure)
10:52:56	TR A				Adjust SP Adjust SF - 28
10:53:48	" "				" " SP=1000
10:54:53	TR P	17.20	~1.6 ppt.		Ad SP & SF - 28
10:56:21					
10:56:52		" 19.40	~4.23		
10:57:50	TR P	20200	5.86		Ad SP Ad SF
10:00:30	P	22900	7.16!		Ad SP
11:01:00					adjusted flow → 45
11:01:47					" " → 28
11:02:14	TR A	24700			adjust SP → 1000mb
11:03:14	P	26000	10.42		" "
11:07:27	TR	25800	10.09		adjust SP → 1000mb
11:13	Transv	25.9	57 ppt		opened Trans ASP properly & adj SP
11:15:20	P1				ad SP
11:16:01	P1	24000'	57.62		" "
11:17:02	P1	23100'			" "
11:17:33	P1				adjust SF
11:18:01	P1	22200	53.71		" "
11:19:07	P1	21200	58.27		" "
11:20:00	P1	20300	63.8		" "
11:21:10	TR	19200	60.2		no SP Ad SF

OZONE ANALYZER LOG

Project: NTERC

Date: 2/3/96

User: JOSS.

Flight No: A445

Page 2 of 3

GMT	RUN #	HEIGHT	OZONE	SCALE	REMARKS (e.g. changes in pressure)
112230	P1	18000	63.48		ad SP $\rightarrow$ 28
112346	P1	16800	60.22		" " "
112455	P1	15500	63.15		" " " no more adjust by.
112736	P1	12900	71.61		adjust SF $\rightarrow$ 28
112846	P1	11600	68.03		" " $\rightarrow$ 28
113438	P1	6000'	58.27		" " $\rightarrow$ 28
113902	P1	3100'	59.24		" " " "
114420	P1	600'	53.71		" " " "
114552	P1 end	100'			" " " $\rightarrow$ 28
114800	P0	100'	52.73		SP = 11.33 EF = 19.03 SF = 80.8
121000	P2	100'	54.04		adjust SF $\rightarrow$ 28
123641	P2	2500	56.64		" " $\rightarrow$ 28
123950	P2	4600'	55.0		" " "
124279	P2	6400'	52.27		adjust SF $\rightarrow$ 1000mb,
124403	P2	8000	60.22		" " " " adjust SF $\rightarrow$ 28
124553	"	9700	64.13		" " " "
124802	"	11900	66.73		" " " "
124929	"	13600	66.41		" " " " ad SF $\rightarrow$ 28
125143	"	15600	61.52		" " " "
125351	"	17700	65.45		" " " "
125555	"	19500	46.87		" " " "

OZONE ANALYZER LOG

Project: NERC

Date: 28/3/96

User: Joss

Flight No: A445

Page 3 of B

GMT	RUN #	HEIGHT	OZONE	SCALE	REMARKS (e.g. changes in pressure)
125717	P2	20800	48.5		adjusted SP to 1000mb
128847	X				" " "
125915	X	17600	53.99		" "
130000	R3	17600	69.34		ad SP ↑ 28
1301	RB	" "	70.64		" " "
130147	R3	" "	84.45		" " ↓ 28
130233	R3	17600	64.45		ad SP ↓ 1000mb
131700	} GPE				
131758					
		14000		range of adjustment	
132204		800?	52 ppb.		ad SP ↑ 28
132406	R4	100'	54.04		" " ↓ 28
135750	P3	7200	57.62		" " "
140009	end P3	10600	67.38		adjusted SP to 1000mb
140115	RS	11000'	69.99		" " " "
140500	RS	11000'	74.54		" " " "
140714	RS	11000'	73.89		" " " "
140908	RS	11000'			" " " "

DATE 20396

500 21000
TI MRF A445

106

NAV CANNING

AIRFIELD B D C

AIRFIELD B D

R/W 23 W/V 310/13 TEMP +5 ONH 1016 OFF 1001

R/W 23 W/V 310/14 TEMP ONH OFF 100

WX 18K 2/200 ILS YED CTN

WX 5/3500 BLU FS.

AIC CL WEST SL

ATC CL

TO TIME 1045

LAND TIME 1435 3:50

TIME	HDG	DR	G/S	IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT/FL	QNH/PR	LAT/LONG	RUN
1143 ³⁶	296	9P	220	178	260	336/60	F260		N 51046 W 04122	P1
46 ¹¹								1021	N 51344 W 06361	-
1147 ⁵⁴	101	15	186	180	181	276/17	100'		N 51329 W 06351	R1
208 ⁰⁵									N 51153 W 04533	-
09 ³	282	5P	157	181	179	291/17	100'		N 51165 W 04526	R2
347									N 51306 W 06280	-
214	271	1P	162	186	187	286/17	50'	1021	N 51309 W 06299	P2
57 ⁷							F210		N 51292 W 06203	-
1301 ¹⁶	101	1P	255	180	235	329/36	F174		N 51275 W 06318	R3
1609							100'		N 51132 W 06450	-
222	290	3P	168	190	186	293/20	100'		N 51131 W 04503	R4
44 ⁵⁵									N 51301 W 06188	-
1347 ⁰⁶	105	0	201	183	182	294/18	800'		N 51327 W 06188	P3
1400 ³³	089	9S	243	188	220	338/44	F110		N 51225 W 05054	R5
1032									N 51108 W 04049	-

1305
N 51300 06150
180

FLIGHT LEADER'S INSTRUMENT STATUS REPORT
=====

FLIGHT NO: *AH45*

DATE: *28 103 196*

MRF

INSTRUMENT	FITTED		OPERATED		COMMENTS
	YES	NO	YES	NO	
NAVIGATION:					
GPS	/				
OMEGA	/				
INU	/				
RADALT	/				
THERMOMETERS:					
DI TEMP	/				
NDI TEMP	/				
ICTP		/			
BARNES ^{Hieman} PRT4	/				
HYGROMETERS:					
GEN. EASTERN	/				
TWC	/				
FWVS		/			
J/W	/				
EXP. PITOT HEAD:					
STATIC PRESS.	/				
PITOT PRESS.	/				
GUST VANES	/				
RADIOMETERS:					
UPPER CLEAR	/				
UPPER RED	/				
UPPER SILICON	/				
LOWER CLEAR	/				
LOWER RED	/				
LOWER SILICON	/				
MARSS		/			
MCR/SAFIRE		/			
DEIMOS	/				
<i>Hieman</i>					
CHEMISTRY:					
OZONE	/				
ECGC		/			
NOX		/			
OTHERS:					
CCN		/			
CLOUD PHYSICS	/				
CABIN PRESS	/				
NEPHELOMETER		/			
HOLOGRAPHY		/			

P.T.O. FAULTS/INCIDENTS

Request to AC MAN Dave Boyde (Hampster) Wants Key to MRF ANTI
ICEING Panel on Forward Bulkhead to carry out Tests.
Need to get into panel to over ride "touch down" relay.

① Heiman CB Left OPEN Pre Mt on JB3
Remuade 1154

② Rear Van DRS Time Display This didget intermittent.

③ 1444. Bird strike on nose.

④ SW - Needle on meter not move ~~prop~~ after take off
so could not zero properly. Cams on in flight.
Values on Horace locked off.

DT 00Z THUR 28/ 3/96 VT 00Z FRI 29/ 3/96 GMAIN T+ 24

--- THICKNESS DM.
HEIGHT DM.

500-1000MB
500MB

MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_6 PAGE.001

28 MAR '96 05:05

POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION 60N SCALE 1:1000000 TIME 03.35 PORT 12 PHE 50 TGR 0020Z

ASXX EGRR MSLP ANALYSIS DT 0000 UTC 28 MAR 1996

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallel 60°N, Original scale 1:20m

28 MAR '96 03:17 FROM MET IT OPS BRACKNELL TO 4806 PAGE.001

** TOTAL PAGE: 001 **

Polar Stereographic Projection. Standard Parallel 60°N. Original scale 1:20m.

ASXX EGRR MSLP ANALYSIS DT 1200 UTC 28 MAR 1996

Polar Stereographic Projection. Standard Parallel 60°N. Original scale 1:20m

A445

GPS data
08:22:50 - 14:41:30

A445

28-MAR-96

13:48:33

036 Ω 51.54

-6.12 FR P

HDG deg T 98.	SPR mb 993.	PHGT kft 0.6	TAS knots 180.	TAT C 4.0	DEW C -1.1	WIND deg m/s 294/9	
---------------------	-------------------	--------------------	----------------------	-----------------	------------------	--------------------------	--

A SELECT	B DEVICE	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
-------------	-------------	-----------	-----------	---	---	------------	-----------

HDC	SPR	PHGT	TAS	TAT	DEL	WIND
degT	mb	hPa	ft/s	C	C	deg/s
99.	946.	1.9	185.	1.1	-2.3	330/9

S. TEMP
C 6.01

A	H	C	D	REF	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	PROP	ZOOM			MODE	HELP

HDC	SPR	PHGT	TAS	TAT	DEW	WIND
deg T	mb	kft	knots	C	C	deg Mph
100.	900.	3.2	192.	-0.5	-4.5	360/9

12.50 WS 9.39

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	AREC	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A445 28-MAR-96 13:55:36 035.0 5.44 5.52 5R 7

HDG degT	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
101.	865.	4.3	191.	-3.1	-6.0	342/ 7

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	PREC	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

HDC	SFR	PHGT	TAS	TAT	DEW	WIND
deg T	mb	kft	knots	C	C	deg MK
100.	800.	6.4	197.	-6.5	-10.5	338/11

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

HDG	SPR	PHGT	TAS	TAT	DEW	WIND
degT	mb	kft	knots	C	C	deg m/s
99.	710.	9.5	202.	-5.6	-37.8	332/17

RADR HGT

0.00

187.50
156.25
125.00
93.75
62.50
31.25
0.00

187.50
156.25
125.00
93.75
62.50
31.25
0.00

1310 1320 1330 1340 1350

A	H	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A445 28-MAR-96 14:00:54 039 51.37 -5.06 ER P

HDG deg T	SRR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
85.	668.	11.1	219.	-7.9	-35.9	338/23

GE DP

A SELECT	B PARAS	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
-------------	------------	-----------	-----------	---	---	------------	-----------

0445 28-MAR-96 14-07-36 039 0 51.36 -4.89 ER P

HDG	SPR	PHGT	TAS	TAT	DEW	WIND
degT	mb	kft	knots	C	C	deg m/s
87.	671.	11.0	210.	-8.0	-36.8	344/21

TWC DP

A B C D E F G H
SELECT PARAS EREC ZOOM VIDEO HELP

A445

28-MAR-96

14:06:30

039 Ω

51.33

-4.49 AS P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
81.	671.	11.0	214.	-8.4	-37.5	346/21

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

HDG degT	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
82.	671.	11.0	221.	-7.9	-38.2	344/22

10:MANZ

-0.04

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms	Form Title
<p style="text-align: center;">1 1 1 1</p>	<p>Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet Aircraft Scientist log Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements sheet Interactive log</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">143 243 1 1</p>	<p>Flight Leader pre-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight log Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">0 0 3+1</p>	<p>SAFIRE log CCN log MARSS log DEIMOS log Chemistry log</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">0 4 — 1 —</p>	<p>Particulate / Filter boom Operator's log 2DC / FSSP / Holography Operator's log Sonde Ejector's log Navigator's log Photographic log (photocopy original)</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">— — — — — —</p>	<p>Instrument status forms RTD prints Raw data plots Weather charts Satellite pictures GPS track</p>

A444 27-MAR-96 10:50:00-13:35:00GMT

mercator projection

INS TRACK - run no

A444 27-MAR-96 Height time series

A445 Profile1

Non Deiced True Temp

Dew Point (GE)

Dew Point (TW)

A445 Profile2

Non Deiced True Temp

Dew Point (GE)

Dew Point (TW)

A445 Profile3

| Non Deiced True Temp

| Dew Point (GE)

| Dew Point (TW)

Meteosat-IR 280596 1300GMT

AUHR
28 MARCH
11:39 AM

AVHRR
28 MARCH 1996
13:19

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R_all

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 11097
Mean 51.3665
Standard dev 0.119338
Max value 51.5727
Min value 51.0505

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 11097
Mean -5.55946
Standard dev 0.745153
Max value -3.55926
Min value -6.87905

CORRECTED NORTH VEL (M S-1)

CORRECTED NORTH VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 735
No. of obs 11097
Mean 1.40013
Standard dev 34.0304
Max value 135.754
Min value -181.004

11:10:00 11:56:15 12:42:30 13:28:45 14:15:00

TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R_all

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 11097
Mean 0.775487
Standard dev 99.1437
Max value 165.512
Min value -142.417

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 11097
Mean 272.750
Standard dev 11.5464
Max value 283.272
Min value 239.137

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 11097
Mean 267.317
Standard dev 13.1254
Max value 279.227
Min value 229.266

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R_all

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 11097
Mean 272.636
Standard dev 11.5650
Max value 283.186
Min value 238.953

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 11097
Mean 267.045
Standard dev 13.1884
Max value 279.021
Min value 228.761

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 11097
Mean 266.402
Standard dev 21.8419
Max value 281.855
Min value 223.088

11:10:00 11:56:15 12:42:30 13:28:45 14:15:00
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R_all

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 11097
Mean 1.98243
Standard dev 1.51348
Max value 19.4677
Min value 0.000000

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 11097
Mean 257.579
Standard dev 16.1514
Max value 273.947
Min value 226.276

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 11097
Mean 245.037
Standard dev 56.1292
Max value 282.516
Min value 0.000000

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R_all

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 11097
Mean 0.967705
Standard dev 7.023402e-02
Max value 1.15062
Min value 0.740267

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 11097
Mean 810.906
Standard dev 219.514
Max value 1020.23
Min value 360.646

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 11097
Mean 57.2012
Standard dev 9.42970
Max value 124.934
Min value 48.6320

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R_all

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 11097
Mean 2118.95
Standard dev 2422.13
Max value 7910.10
Min value -57.9665

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 11097
Mean 612.396
Standard dev 687.440
Max value 1522.15
Min value 0.000000

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 11097
Mean 5.79527
Standard dev 4.14880
Max value 164.746
Min value 3.423831e-02

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R_all

UPP VIS CLR SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 673
No. of obs 11097
Mean 762.622
Standard dev 94.0539
Max value 1271.91
Min value 111.766

UPP VIS RED SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 674
No. of obs 11097
Mean 380.339
Standard dev 52.8102
Max value 652.834
Min value 21.6580

UPP I/R SIGNAL (W M-2)

Parameter no. 675
No. of obs 11097
Mean 993.810
Standard dev 20.3207
Max value 1044.01
Min value 936.915

11:10:00 11:56:15 12:42:30 13:28:45 14:15:00
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R_all

UPP VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 679
No. of obs 11097
Mean 274.426
Standard dev 11.4383
Max value 284.378
Min value 241.977

UPP VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 680
No. of obs 11097
Mean 272.704
Standard dev 11.9582
Max value 283.007
Min value 238.968

UPP I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 681
No. of obs 11097
Mean 272.351
Standard dev 12.0905
Max value 282.717
Min value 238.077

11:10:00 11:56:15 12:42:30 13:28:45 14:15:00
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R_all

LWR VIS CLR SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 682
No. of obs 11097
Mean 118.329
Standard dev 41.0253
Max value 435.484
Min value 67.3387

LWR VIS RED SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 683
No. of obs 11097
Mean 53.3389
Standard dev 22.0981
Max value 198.942
Min value 20.4568

LWR I/R SIGNAL (WM-2)

Parameter no. 684
No. of obs 11097
Mean 502.188
Standard dev 26.8960
Max value 583.201
Min value 470.701

11:10:00 11:56:15 12:42:30 13:28:45 14:15:00
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R_all

LWR VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 688
No. of obs 11097
Mean 272.167
Standard dev 11.8341
Max value 282.341
Min value 238.620

LWR VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 689
No. of obs 11097
Mean 273.307
Standard dev 12.2114
Max value 283.831
Min value 238.680

LWR I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 690
No. of obs 11097
Mean 272.498
Standard dev 12.0479
Max value 282.838
Min value 238.072

1 second averages

11:10:00 11:56:15 12:42:30 13:28:45 14:15:00
TIME (GMT)

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R_all

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 11097
Mean 339.853
Standard dev 228.018
Max value 991.172
Min value 3.00000

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 11097
Mean 0.102133
Standard dev 1.377709e-02
Max value 0.212600
Min value 6.496817e-02

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 11097
Mean 3.70020
Standard dev 3.91422
Max value 35.5799
Min value 3.751399e-03

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R_all

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 11097
Mean 0.124921
Standard dev 3.928104e-02
Max value 0.636080
Min value 6.684455e-02

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 11097
Mean 0.110703
Standard dev 2.142246e-02
Max value 0.440607
Min value 6.604987e-02

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 11097
Mean 0.167251
Standard dev 0.119595
Max value 1.32510
Min value 6.811145e-02

11:10:00 11:56:15 12:42:30 13:28:45 14:15:00
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P1

Times 11:14:35-11:46:11 GMT

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P1

Times 11:14:35-11:46:11 GMT

1 second averages

TW

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P1

Times 11:14:35-11:46:11 GMT

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P1

Times 11:14:35-11:46:11 GMT

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P1

Times 11:14:35-11:46:11 GMT

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)
Parameter no. 524

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
Parameter no. 525

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)
Parameter no. 537

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P1

Times 11:14:35-11:46:11 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

0.0 2.5 5.0
TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)
Parameter no. 572

200 250 300
DEW POINT (DEG K)
Parameter no. 529

200 250 300
TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)
Parameter no. 725

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P1

Times 11:14:35-11:46:11 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P1

Times 11:14:35-11:46:11 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P1

Times 11:14:35-11:46:11 GMT

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P2

Times 12:32:14-12:57:37 GMT

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P2

Times 12:32:14-12:57:37 GMT

1 second averages

TW

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P2

Times 12:32:14-12:57:37 GMT

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P2

Times 12:32:14-12:57:37 GMT

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731

CORRECTED NORTH VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 735

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P2

Times 12:32:14-12:57:37 GMT

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P2

Times 12:32:14-12:57:37 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P2

Times 12:32:14-12:57:37 GMT

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)
Parameter no. 572

DEW POINT (DEG K)
Parameter no. 529

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)
Parameter no. 725

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P2

Times 12:32:14-12:57:37 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P2

Times 12:32:14-12:57:37 GMT

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P2

Times 12:32:14-12:57:37 GMT

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P3

Times 13:47:06-14:00:33 GMT

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P3

Times 13:47:06-14:00:33 GMT

1 second averages

TW

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P3

Times 13:47:06-14:00:33 GMT

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P3

Times 13:47:06-14:00:33 GMT

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P3

Times 13:47:06-14:00:33 GMT

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P3

Times 13:47:06-14:00:33 GMT

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P3

Times 13:47:06-14:00:33 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P3

Times 13:47:06-14:00:33 GMT

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P3

Times 13:47:06-14:00:33 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96 Profile P3

Times 13:47:06-14:00:33 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R1

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 1217
Mean 281.485
Standard dev 8.74734
Max value 309.462
Min value 262.058

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 1217
Mean 8.10482
Standard dev 0.703688
Max value 10.0757
Min value 6.01628

WIND COMP (METRES/S)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 1217
Mean north -1.54742
Stan dev north 1.14660
Max north 1.15180
Min north -4.61167
Mean east -1.54742
Stan dev east 1.14660
Max east 1.15180
Min east -4.61167

11:47:59 11:53:03 11:58:07 12:03:11 12:08:15
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R1

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 1217
Mean 51.3892
Standard dev 8.817536e-02
Max value 51.5366
Min value 51.2456

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 1217
Mean -5.73522
Standard dev 0.486196
Max value -4.89246
Min value -6.58436

CORRECTED NORTH VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 735
No. of obs 1217
Mean -26.5814
Standard dev 4.16026
Max value -17.2899
Min value -34.9692

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R1

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 1217
Mean 96.4664
Standard dev 1.64541
Max value 101.330
Min value 93.3737

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 1217
Mean 282.121
Standard dev 0.149528
Max value 282.707
Min value 281.679

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 1217
Mean 278.094
Standard dev 0.101003
Max value 278.472
Min value 277.776

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R1

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 1217
Mean 282.021
Standard dev 0.153363
Max value 282.625
Min value 281.570

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 1217
Mean 277.875
Standard dev 0.104167
Max value 278.264
Min value 277.553

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 1217
Mean 268.624
Standard dev 22.9750
Max value 281.855
Min value 223.088

1 second averages

11:47:59 11:53:03 11:58:07 12:03:11 12:08:15
TIME (GMT)

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R1

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 1217
Mean 3.25334
Standard dev 0.124271
Max value 3.69733
Min value 2.87955

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 1217
Mean 271.793
Standard dev 0.433012
Max value 273.298
Min value 270.407

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 1217
Mean 271.261
Standard dev 0.513644
Max value 273.019
Min value 269.607

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R1

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 1217
Mean 0.916064
Standard dev 8.421363e-03
Max value 0.935919
Min value 0.875818

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 1217
Mean 1017.30
Standard dev 0.363247
Max value 1018.09
Min value 1015.63

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 1217
Mean 54.9584
Standard dev 1.21635
Max value 59.9279
Min value 51.8856

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R1

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 1217
Mean -33.6383
Standard dev 3.01427
Max value -19.8029
Min value -40.2132

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 1217
Mean 32.2099
Standard dev 2.52469
Max value 42.5800
Min value 27.3401

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 1217
Mean 7.78557
Standard dev 0.226189
Max value 8.35704
Min value 7.33852

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R1

UPP VIS CLR SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 673
No. of obs 1217
Mean 730.960
Standard dev 21.2608
Max value 826.376
Min value 618.538

UPP VIS RED SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 674
No. of obs 1217
Mean 364.479
Standard dev 9.98854
Max value 418.132
Min value 295.256

UPP I/R SIGNAL (W M-2)

Parameter no. 675
No. of obs 1217
Mean 1011.42
Standard dev 1.52548
Max value 1016.00
Min value 1008.31

11:47:59 11:53:03 11:58:07 12:03:11 12:08:15

TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R1

UPP VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 679
No. of obs 1217
Mean 283.341
Standard dev 0.285215
Max value 283.653
Min value 282.249

UPP VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 680
No. of obs 1217
Mean 282.215
Standard dev 0.399287
Max value 282.584
Min value 280.753

UPP I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 681
No. of obs 1217
Mean 281.929
Standard dev 0.310271
Max value 282.200
Min value 280.698

11:47:59 11:53:03 11:58:07 12:03:11 12:08:15
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R1

LWR VIS CLR SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 682
No. of obs 1217
Mean 92.8145
Standard dev 1.58403
Max value 97.5807
Min value 85.0807

LWR VIS RED SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 683
No. of obs 1217
Mean 46.6300
Standard dev 1.15561
Max value 49.3520
Min value 42.9593

LWR I/R SIGNAL (WM-2)

Parameter no. 684
No. of obs 1217
Mean 485.458
Standard dev 1.83913
Max value 490.182
Min value 480.928

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R1

LWR VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 688
No. of obs 1217
Mean 281.497
Standard dev 0.227376
Max value 281.705
Min value 280.525

LWR VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 689
No. of obs 1217
Mean 282.884
Standard dev 0.276114
Max value 283.107
Min value 281.755

LWR I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 690
No. of obs 1217
Mean 282.019
Standard dev 0.191284
Max value 282.194
Min value 281.137

11:47:59 11:53:03 11:58:07 12:03:11 12:08:15
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R1

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 1217
Mean 583.599
Standard dev 62.9083
Max value 763.152
Min value 379.065

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 1217
Mean 0.112618
Standard dev 2.552940e-03
Max value 0.120887
Min value 0.104197

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 1217
Mean 6.63841
Standard dev 3.37155
Max value 28.1142
Min value 2.56321

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R1

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 1217
Mean 0.136661
Standard dev 1.954507e-02
Max value 0.220166
Min value 0.113222

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 1217
Mean 0.120797
Standard dev 5.578317e-03
Max value 0.147017
Min value 0.108859

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 1217
Mean 0.180114
Standard dev 6.836528e-02
Max value 0.510899
Min value 0.121913

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R2

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 1333
Mean 296.230
Standard dev 6.66158
Max value 315.216
Min value 277.697

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 1333
Mean 9.02550
Standard dev 0.764757
Max value 11.1041
Min value 6.84604

WIND COMP (METRES/S)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 1333
Mean north -3.94497
Stan dev north 0.914761
Max north -1.16167
Min north -6.30788
Mean east -3.94497
Stan dev east 0.914761
Max east -1.16167
Min east -6.30788

1 second averages

12:09:35 12:15:08 12:20:41 12:26:14 12:31:47
TIME (GMT)

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R2

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 1333
Mean 51.3816
Standard dev 6.584538e-02
Max value 51.4993
Min value 51.2687

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 1333
Mean -5.67294
Standard dev 0.453799
Max value -4.88480
Min value -6.45722

CORRECTED NORTH VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 735
No. of obs 1333
Mean 19.2374
Standard dev 1.88899
Max value 24.5349
Min value 13.4095

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R2

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 1333
Mean -81.8601
Standard dev 2.22548
Max value -75.8925
Min value -87.6274

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 1333
Mean 282.324
Standard dev 0.240255
Max value 282.912
Min value 281.647

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 1333
Mean 278.233
Standard dev 0.137415
Max value 278.655
Min value 277.836

12:09:35 12:15:08 12:20:41 12:26:14 12:31:47
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R2

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 1333
Mean 282.227
Standard dev 0.241840
Max value 282.828
Min value 281.541

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 1333
Mean 278.015
Standard dev 0.139120
Max value 278.460
Min value 277.643

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 1333
Mean 275.068
Standard dev 38.8155
Max value 281.135
Min value 0.000000

12:09:35 12:15:08 12:20:41 12:26:14 12:31:47
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R2

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 1333
Mean 3.39966
Standard dev 0.130370
Max value 3.86947
Min value 3.00716

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 1333
Mean 272.022
Standard dev 0.388984
Max value 273.234
Min value 270.447

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 1333
Mean 271.865
Standard dev 0.519028
Max value 273.652
Min value 270.203

12:09:35 12:15:08 12:20:41 12:26:14 12:31:47

TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R2

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 1333
Mean 0.910882
Standard dev 1.112055e-02
Max value 0.944346
Min value 0.876513

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 1333
Mean 1017.67
Standard dev 0.340054
Max value 1018.41
Min value 1016.73

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 1333
Mean 55.8412
Standard dev 2.51428
Max value 62.1202
Min value 48.7813

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R2

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 1333
Mean -36.7165
Standard dev 2.82027
Max value -28.9673
Min value -42.8360

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 1333
Mean 31.3217
Standard dev 1.51182
Max value 36.2610
Min value 25.2958

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 1333
Mean 6.88013
Standard dev 0.208273
Max value 7.56403
Min value 6.47988

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R2

UPP VIS CLR SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 673
No. of obs 1333
Mean 752.775
Standard dev 16.0357
Max value 788.483
Min value 568.780

UPP VIS RED SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 674
No. of obs 1333
Mean 372.940
Standard dev 7.61718
Max value 388.960
Min value 272.714

UPP I/R SIGNAL (W M-2)

Parameter no. 675
No. of obs 1333
Mean 1012.31
Standard dev 1.12035
Max value 1016.00
Min value 1009.96

12:09:35 12:15:08 12:20:41 12:26:14 12:31:47
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R2

UPP VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 679
No. of obs 1333
Mean 283.910
Standard dev 0.220881
Max value 284.151
Min value 283.110

UPP VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 680
No. of obs 1333
Mean 282.534
Standard dev 0.164818
Max value 282.772
Min value 282.021

UPP I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 681
No. of obs 1333
Mean 282.236
Standard dev 0.203104
Max value 282.482
Min value 281.590

1 second averages

12:09:35 12:15:08 12:20:41 12:26:14 12:31:47
TIME (GMT)

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R2

LWR VIS CLR SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 682
No. of obs 1333
Mean 92.7643
Standard dev 1.43934
Max value 97.5807
Min value 81.4516

LWR VIS RED SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 683
No. of obs 1333
Mean 45.9384
Standard dev 0.692008
Max value 48.8406
Min value 40.6579

LWR I/R SIGNAL (WM-2)

Parameter no. 684
No. of obs 1333
Mean 484.896
Standard dev 1.89162
Max value 488.477
Min value 480.685

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R2

LWR VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 688
No. of obs 1333
Mean 281.774
Standard dev 0.203836
Max value 282.068
Min value 281.115

LWR VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 689
No. of obs 1333
Mean 283.218
Standard dev 0.201038
Max value 283.493
Min value 282.575

LWR I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 690
No. of obs 1333
Mean 282.234
Standard dev 0.203328
Max value 282.516
Min value 281.551

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R2

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 1333
Mean 503.449
Standard dev 51.7939
Max value 679.441
Min value 318.286

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 1333
Mean 0.112865
Standard dev 2.713113e-03
Max value 0.123256
Min value 0.105174

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 1333
Mean 6.13257
Standard dev 3.47419
Max value 26.8552
Min value 2.35704

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R2

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 1333
Mean 0.139209
Standard dev 2.245393e-02
Max value 0.234627
Min value 0.114331

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 1333
Mean 0.121675
Standard dev 6.446344e-03
Max value 0.148608
Min value 0.110654

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 1333
Mean 0.188895
Standard dev 7.997558e-02
Max value 0.584585
Min value 0.121997

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R3

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 934
Mean 325.399
Standard dev 3.06266
Max value 331.907
Min value 320.793

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 934
Mean 22.6671
Standard dev 2.39347
Max value 26.8801
Min value 18.8466

WIND COMP (METRES/S)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 934
Mean north -18.5653
Stan dev north 1.36780
Max north -16.2180
Min north -21.5318
Mean east -18.5653
Stan dev east 1.36780
Max east -16.2180
Min east -21.5318

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R3

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 934
Mean 51.2954
Standard dev 7.474800e-02
Max value 51.4445
Min value 51.1989

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 934
Mean -5.63980
Standard dev 0.521222
Max value -4.73092
Min value -6.53030

CORRECTED NORTH VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 735
No. of obs 934
Mean -29.2178
Standard dev 12.8631
Max value -12.6010
Min value -41.8686

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R3

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 934
Mean 134.005
Standard dev 3.40467
Max value 140.676
Min value 125.199

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 934
Mean 258.064
Standard dev 0.489611
Max value 258.937
Min value 257.036

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 934
Mean 250.965
Standard dev 0.354274
Max value 251.453
Min value 250.184

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

13:01:16 13:05:09 13:09:02 13:12:55 13:16:49
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R3

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 934
Mean 257.916
Standard dev 0.491367
Max value 258.800
Min value 256.883

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 934
Mean 250.611
Standard dev 0.354393
Max value 251.101
Min value 249.831

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 934
Mean 275.995
Standard dev 1.06169
Max value 276.811
Min value 266.794

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R3

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 934
Mean 0.481123
Standard dev 5.261624e-02
Max value 0.581678
Min value 0.373321

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 934
Mean 244.532
Standard dev 1.22468
Max value 246.731
Min value 241.678

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 934
Mean 240.108
Standard dev 1.19115
Max value 242.204
Min value 237.502

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R3

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 934
Mean 1.06131
Standard dev 7.232658e-03
Max value 1.08204
Min value 1.03658

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 934
Mean 517.245
Standard dev 0.189887
Max value 517.970
Min value 516.713

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 934
Mean 55.5803
Standard dev 2.13700
Max value 60.5537
Min value 51.3022

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R3

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 934
Mean 5323.51
Standard dev 2.72358
Max value 5331.15
Min value 5313.11

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 934
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 934
Mean 3.95244
Standard dev 0.153761
Max value 4.36477
Min value 3.59987

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R3

UPP VIS CLR SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 673
No. of obs 934
Mean 828.670
Standard dev 17.8015
Max value 843.601
Min value 675.570

UPP VIS RED SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 674
No. of obs 934
Mean 409.711
Standard dev 10.9994
Max value 422.110
Min value 325.091

UPP I/R SIGNAL (W M-2)

Parameter no. 675
No. of obs 934
Mean 971.319
Standard dev 1.69632
Max value 977.005
Min value 968.218

13:01:16 13:05:09 13:09:02 13:12:55 13:16:49
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R3

UPP VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 679
No. of obs 934
Mean 261.320
Standard dev 0.386684
Max value 261.819
Min value 260.460

UPP VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 680
No. of obs 934
Mean 259.185
Standard dev 0.348826
Max value 259.626
Min value 258.452

UPP I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 681
No. of obs 934
Mean 258.648
Standard dev 0.306057
Max value 259.059
Min value 257.979

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R3

LWR VIS CLR SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 682
No. of obs 934
Mean 130.788
Standard dev 6.31038
Max value 147.177
Min value 122.581

LWR VIS RED SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 683
No. of obs 934
Mean 51.2644
Standard dev 3.98880
Max value 60.6033
Min value 43.9821

LWR I/R SIGNAL (WM-2)

Parameter no. 684
No. of obs 934
Mean 533.391
Standard dev 1.03388
Max value 536.935
Min value 531.334

1 second averages

13:01:16 13:05:09 13:09:02 13:12:55 13:16:49
TIME (GMT)

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R3

LWR VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 688
No. of obs 934
Mean 258.346
Standard dev 0.280143
Max value 258.733
Min value 257.688

LWR VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 689
No. of obs 934
Mean 259.288
Standard dev 0.280286
Max value 259.686
Min value 258.624

LWR I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 690
No. of obs 934
Mean 258.534
Standard dev 0.296477
Max value 258.984
Min value 257.881

13:01:16 13:05:09 13:09:02 13:12:55 13:16:49

TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R3

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 934
Mean 292.488
Standard dev 73.3640
Max value 479.065
Min value 129.463

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 934
Mean 9.296309e-02
Standard dev 3.253182e-03
Max value 0.101797
Min value 8.194175e-02

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 934
Mean 1.67238
Standard dev 1.32779
Max value 12.6031
Min value 0.526438

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R3

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 934
Mean 0.107854
Standard dev 1.702647e-02
Max value 0.240977
Min value 9.011835e-02

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 934
Mean 9.914106e-02
Standard dev 5.548428e-03
Max value 0.137966
Min value 8.590537e-02

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 934
Mean 0.131985
Standard dev 6.871340e-02
Max value 0.734824
Min value 9.891400e-02

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R4

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 1295
Mean 294.747
Standard dev 5.21349
Max value 310.719
Min value 280.127

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 1295
Mean 9.60604
Standard dev 0.645363
Max value 11.4046
Min value 7.32603

WIND COMP (METRES/S)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 1295
Mean north -4.01276
Stan dev north 0.879701
Max north -1.64317
Min north -7.26180
Mean east -4.01276
Stan dev east 0.879701
Max east -1.64317
Min east -7.26180

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R4

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 1295
Mean 51.3624
Standard dev 7.842099e-02
Max value 51.4883
Min value 51.2261

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 1295
Mean -5.55525
Standard dev 0.426202
Max value -4.81356
Min value -6.29855

CORRECTED NORTH VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 735
No. of obs 1295
Mean 22.5144
Standard dev 4.71367
Max value 30.3005
Min value 1.75149

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R4

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 1295
Mean -79.6128
Standard dev 1.95866
Max value -75.7277
Min value -85.7517

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 1295
Mean 282.731
Standard dev 0.175294
Max value 283.272
Min value 282.256

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 1295
Mean 278.688
Standard dev 0.161434
Max value 279.227
Min value 278.258

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R4

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 1295
Mean 282.636
Standard dev 0.180395
Max value 283.186
Min value 282.151

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 1295
Mean 278.473
Standard dev 0.167086
Max value 279.021
Min value 278.039

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 1295
Mean 255.590
Standard dev 78.6750
Max value 280.445
Min value 0.000000

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R4

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 1295
Mean 3.66433
Standard dev 0.146655
Max value 4.17950
Min value 3.32254

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 1295
Mean 272.736
Standard dev 0.390335
Max value 273.947
Min value 271.873

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 1295
Mean 272.887
Standard dev 0.545967
Max value 274.714
Min value 271.563

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

13:23:21

13:28:44

13:34:08

13:39:31

13:44:55

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R4

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 1295
Mean 0.902425
Standard dev 1.077361e-02
Max value 0.934852
Min value 0.850924

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 1295
Mean 1017.44
Standard dev 0.329444
Max value 1018.23
Min value 1016.01

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 1295
Mean 55.0783
Standard dev 1.94896
Max value 62.4037
Min value 49.9151

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R4

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 1295
Mean -34.8026
Standard dev 2.73322
Max value -22.9697
Min value -41.3558

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 1295
Mean 32.0413
Standard dev 2.70232
Max value 42.5800
Min value 26.5967

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 1295
Mean 7.28336
Standard dev 0.168798
Max value 7.67016
Min value 6.62345

1 second average

TIME (GMT)

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R4

UPP VIS CLR SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 673
No. of obs 1295
Mean 710.928
Standard dev 37.1198
Max value 799.583
Min value 331.086

UPP VIS RED SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 674
No. of obs 1295
Mean 346.385
Standard dev 22.7892
Max value 396.253
Min value 130.832

UPP I/R SIGNAL (W M-2)

Parameter no. 675
No. of obs 1295
Mean 1010.30
Standard dev 2.15625
Max value 1016.55
Min value 1005.56

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R4

UPP VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 679
No. of obs 1295
Mean 283.620
Standard dev 0.687443
Max value 284.378
Min value 280.890

UPP VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 680
No. of obs 1295
Mean 282.113
Standard dev 0.869141
Max value 283.007
Min value 278.922

UPP I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 681
No. of obs 1295
Mean 282.016
Standard dev 0.812161
Max value 282.717
Min value 278.680

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R4

LWR VIS CLR SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 682
No. of obs 1295
Mean 92.4760
Standard dev 4.22233
Max value 112.500
Min value 67.3387

LWR VIS RED SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 683
No. of obs 1295
Mean 44.9978
Standard dev 4.15716
Max value 54.4662
Min value 24.2924

LWR I/R SIGNAL (WM-2)

Parameter no. 684
No. of obs 1295
Mean 483.807
Standard dev 2.27364
Max value 492.617
Min value 479.224

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R4

LWR VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 688
No. of obs 1295
Mean 281.730
Standard dev 0.704390
Max value 282.341
Min value 278.890

LWR VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 689
No. of obs 1295
Mean 283.122
Standard dev 0.752591
Max value 283.831
Min value 280.113

LWR I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 690
No. of obs 1295
Mean 282.358
Standard dev 0.534128
Max value 282.838
Min value 279.896

1 second averages

13:23:21 13:28:44 13:34:08 13:39:31 13:44:55
TIME (GMT)

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R4

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 1295
Mean 562.555
Standard dev 65.3839
Max value 880.536
Min value 388.513

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 1295
Mean 0.114997
Standard dev 3.107336e-03
Max value 0.127678
Min value 0.103952

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 1295
Mean 7.27742
Standard dev 4.04833
Max value 35.5799
Min value 3.02429

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R4

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 1295
Mean 0.142074
Standard dev 2.237530e-02
Max value 0.251791
Min value 0.113010

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 1295
Mean 0.124079
Standard dev 6.587625e-03
Max value 0.160148
Min value 0.108499

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 1295
Mean 0.192746
Standard dev 7.943153e-02
Max value 0.622131
Min value 0.122544

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R5

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 600
Mean 342.531
Standard dev 2.83674
Max value 346.436
Min value 335.574

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 600
Mean 21.1261
Standard dev 0.592107
Max value 22.7548
Min value 19.7126

WIND COMP (METRES/S)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 600
Mean north -20.1204
Stan dev north 0.395605
Max north -19.0149
Min north -21.0523
Mean east -20.1204
Stan dev east 0.395605
Max east -19.0149
Min east -21.0523

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R5

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 600
Mean 51.3071
Standard dev 1.369735e-02
Max value 51.3381
Min value 51.2908

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 600
Mean -4.55718
Standard dev 0.289176
Max value -4.06176
Min value -5.06232

CORRECTED NORTH VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 735
No. of obs 600
Mean -8.75296
Standard dev 5.67769
Max value -2.70881
Min value -19.8659

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R5

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 600
Mean 116.015
Standard dev 3.05846
Max value 122.979
Min value 111.099

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 600
Mean 270.857
Standard dev 0.540074
Max value 271.635
Min value 269.575

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 600
Mean 265.074
Standard dev 0.395649
Max value 265.549
Min value 263.961

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R5

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 600
Mean 270.740
Standard dev 0.547188
Max value 271.541
Min value 269.432

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 600
Mean 264.788
Standard dev 0.399078
Max value 265.266
Min value 263.634

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 600
Mean 274.569
Standard dev 3.50545
Max value 277.128
Min value 263.117

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R5

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 600
Mean 0.213805
Standard dev 2.507790e-02
Max value 0.247565
Min value 0.143947

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 600
Mean 236.047
Standard dev 0.638780
Max value 237.297
Min value 234.822

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 600
Mean 234.389
Standard dev 1.31399
Max value 235.920
Min value 230.517

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R5

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 600
Mean 1.04518
Standard dev 9.427171e-03
Max value 1.07778
Min value 1.01461

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 600
Mean 672.140
Standard dev 0.710158
Max value 673.426
Min value 669.296

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 600
Mean 55.2353
Standard dev 2.15912
Max value 58.9351
Min value 51.3502

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R5

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 600
Mean 3330.18
Standard dev 8.24976
Max value 3363.24
Min value 3315.27

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 600
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 600
Mean 4.67240
Standard dev 0.184300
Max value 4.98687
Min value 4.18806

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R5

UPP VIS CLR SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 673
No. of obs 600
Mean 758.321
Standard dev 10.6578
Max value 794.225
Min value 700.449

UPP VIS RED SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 674
No. of obs 600
Mean 388.920
Standard dev 5.88708
Max value 409.734
Min value 352.716

UPP I/R SIGNAL (W M-2)

Parameter no. 675
No. of obs 600
Mean 970.948
Standard dev 3.04474
Max value 975.358
Min value 962.177

1 second drag

TIME (SMT)

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R5

UPP VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 679
No. of obs 600
Mean 274.042
Standard dev 0.620368
Max value 275.726
Min value 273.053

UPP VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 680
No. of obs 600
Mean 272.588
Standard dev 0.711202
Max value 274.415
Min value 271.457

UPP I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 681
No. of obs 600
Mean 272.078
Standard dev 0.684947
Max value 273.939
Min value 271.076

1 second averages

A445 28-MAR-96

Run no. R5

LWR VIS CLR SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 682
No. of obs 600
Mean 153.821
Standard dev 48.8046
Max value 329.436
Min value 120.968

LWR VIS RED SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 683
No. of obs 600
Mean 67.7418
Standard dev 25.4176
Max value 159.819
Min value 51.6534

LWR I/R SIGNAL (WM-2)

Parameter no. 684
No. of obs 600
Mean 492.644
Standard dev 6.44346
Max value 498.461
Min value 473.380

14:00:33 14:03:02 14:05:32 14:08:02 14:10:32

TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

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Run no. R5

LWR VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 688
No. of obs 600
Mean 271.731
Standard dev 0.634340
Max value 273.397
Min value 270.764

LWR VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 689
No. of obs 600
Mean 273.007
Standard dev 0.649650
Max value 274.752
Min value 272.048

LWR I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 690
No. of obs 600
Mean 271.926
Standard dev 0.590527
Max value 273.599
Min value 271.026

1 second averages

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Run no. R5

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 600
Mean 70.3162
Standard dev 18.9036
Max value 145.241
Min value 35.0137

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 600
Mean $8.658011e-02$
Standard dev $6.830036e-03$
Max value 0.117787
Min value $7.336724e-02$

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 600
Mean 0.684693
Standard dev 1.65221
Max value 11.4357
Min value 0.102618

1 second averages

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Run no. R5

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 600
Mean 0.109697
Standard dev 4.706743e-02
Max value 0.378023
Min value 7.800549e-02

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 600
Mean 9.573987e-02
Standard dev 2.024843e-02
Max value 0.212079
Min value 7.555735e-02

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 600
Mean 0.159057
Standard dev 0.173889
Max value 1.20051
Min value 8.310157e-02

